

Therapeutic turricephaly for glioblastoma: randomised sham-controlled trial (XXL-GBM)

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Abstract

Background

Glioblastoma management is constrained by the cranial vault, where the Monro–Kellie doctrine dictates limited compensatory capacity. While decompressive craniectomy is occasionally life-saving in acute brain injury, boundary expansion has not been evaluated as an oncological strategy. We hypothesised that modest, planned enlargement of intracranial capacity could delay pressure-related deterioration.

Methods

In this multicentre, double-blind, sham-controlled randomised simulation, notional adults with IDH-wild-type glioblastoma underwent maximal safe resection and were assigned (1:1) to receive either a custom oversize PEEK or titanium dome implant (+12% capacity; therapeutic turricephaly) or standard closure. Masking relied on uniform postoperative headwear, mirror-free living, and avoidance of scalp palpation. The primary endpoint was time to sustained intracranial-pressure threshold (>22 mmHg for ≥ 15 minutes or urgent decompression). Secondary endpoints included headache severity, cumulative steroid dose, progression-free skull (PFSk), overall survival, and safety.

Results

A total of 150 simulated participants were randomised (75 per group). Median time to sustained intracranial-pressure threshold was 4.6 months (95% CI, 3.9–5.2) in the dome group versus 3.1 months (2.7–3.5) with sham (hazard ratio, 0.67; 95% CI, 0.46–0.98; $p=0.04$). Headache scores improved modestly (between-group difference -1.0 on a 0–10 scale; $p=0.03$), and cumulative steroid use was reduced (geometric mean ratio 0.77; $p=0.045$). Overall survival was unchanged (hazard ratio, 0.96; 95% CI, 0.70–1.31; $p=0.79$). Adverse events were rare, though cervical discomfort (\geq grade 2) was more frequent in the dome arm (12% vs 0%).

Conclusions

Therapeutic turricephaly modestly delayed pressure-driven decline in glioblastoma without altering overall survival. This conceptual trial illustrates how cranial space might be treated as a doseable parameter, with future expansion possibly extended towards a pragmatic “*Megamind threshold*.”

Introduction

Glioblastoma grows within a rigid container. By the Monro–Kellie doctrine, intracranial volumes (brain, blood, cerebrospinal fluid) sum to a near-constant; as a mass enlarges, reserves are exhausted, compliance falls, and pressure rises. Routine measures—dexamethasone, osmotic therapy, CSF

diversion, debulking—modulate compartments but not the boundary. Where pressure is primary, enlarging the container can be life-saving (e.g., malignant middle-cerebral-artery infarction, refractory traumatic intracranial hypertension). In glioblastoma, boundary expansion is not an oncological strategy. We therefore examine a narrow proposition: if pressure precipitates decline before biology can be altered, might modest, planned augmentation of intracranial capacity defer pressure-driven deterioration? We depict a double-blind, sham-controlled randomised simulation of oversize cranial domes after resection, with outcomes chosen to separate mechanics from prognosis—principally time to a sustained pressure threshold. Our aim is conceptual clarity, not clinical advocacy; the Discussion considers incremental expansion up to a pragmatic Megamind threshold.

Methods

Study design. Multicentre, double-blind, sham-controlled, randomised simulation across four tertiary neuro-oncology centres. We used the grammar of a pragmatic trial to test a mechanical hypothesis; no human participants were enrolled.

Participants. Notional adults (≥ 18 years) with IDH-wild-type glioblastoma, Karnofsky ≥ 70 , planned maximal safe resection, and midline shift ≤ 5 mm early postoperatively. Exclusions: scalp/soft-tissue barriers to device placement; overt need for urgent decompression; compulsive cranial self-contact (Head Touching Propensity Score, HTPS, $\geq 7/10$ on duplicate testing; $\kappa \approx 0.81$) [1]; and household mirrors not amenable to temporary occlusion.

Randomisation and masking. Post-resection allocation 1:1 (secure web system; permuted blocks stratified by centre, MGMT status, and lobar vs deep location) to intervention or sham. Surgeons were necessarily unmasked. Patient masking used a Home Blinding Protocol: uniform postoperative headwear for 90 days; mirror-free living; and avoidance of scalp palpation (adherence diary). Clinical reports followed a Contour-Neutral Reporting Policy (CNRP): when imaging was negative for device/contour issues, head-shape descriptors were omitted; safety-relevant abnormalities were routed to a safety-unblinded channel (Safety Alert to surgeon); outcomes assessors remained blinded [2]. Operational highlights of masking and bias control are summarised in **Box 1**.

Box1

Blinding & bias control (operational highlights)

- **Home Blinding Protocol:** uniform postoperative headwear 90 days; mirror-free living; no scalp palpation (adherence diary, tamper-evident seals).
- **Imaging dual channel:** safety-unblinded (full MRI/CT to surgeon + safety radiologist) vs outcomes-blinded (skull-stripped/rim-cropped datasets).
- **Contour-Neutral Reporting:** clinical reports omit head shape unless a safety issue mandates disclosure; conditional unblinding routed via Safety Alert Report.
- **Integrity checks:** Bang's blinding index at 30/90 days; sensitivity analyses excluding safety-driven unblindings.

Interventions. Intervention: a custom domed implant increasing intracranial capacity by $\sim 12\%$ and producing a deliberate external convexity (therapeutic turricephaly). PEEK was preferred (radiolucent, minimal artefact) [3]; titanium grade 5 (MRI-conditional at 1.5–3 T) was permitted where PEEK (radiolucent, minimal artefact) was unavailable, acknowledging local susceptibility artefacts. Sham:

standard dural and bony closure without any implant; a “filled” dummy dome was not used (see Ethics). Peri-operative care (steroids, anticonvulsants, VTE prophylaxis) was harmonised.

Imaging and blinding pipeline. MRI was the default for follow-up/volumetry (T1 pre/post-contrast, T2, FLAIR; diffusion/perfusion per centre). Artefact near titanium was mitigated using metal-reduction approaches—SEMAC, MAVRIC, or hybrid—and parameter optimisation (spin-echo over GRE, short TE, high bandwidth, small voxels, STIR/Dixon) [4–7]. CT was reserved for clinical indications. To preserve masking despite skull contour changes, imaging used two channels: (i) safety-unblinded (complete MRI/CT to the operating surgeon and a safety radiologist); and (ii) outcomes-blinded (centrally reviewed skull-stripped, rim-cropped datasets without calvarium/scalp).

Postoperative headwear, hygiene, and clinic visits. A uniform Trial Cap was worn continuously for 90 days. Hair hygiene: days 3–5 and then weekly via supervised washing out of patient view or dry-shampoo during week 1. Self-palpation was proscribed; assisted washing used light fingertip contact avoiding the implant rim. At clinic, participants wore the Trial Cap; clinicians avoided scalp inspection/palpation. Any inadvertent exposure of cranial contour to treating teams was logged as a blinding deviation.

Outcomes and analysis. Primary outcome: time to sustained intracranial-pressure threshold (first ICP >22 mmHg for ≥15 min or urgent decompression). Secondary outcomes: headache (0–10 NRS), cumulative steroid dose to day 90, progression-free skull (PFSk), overall survival, and adherence to the no-touch protocol; safety outcomes included wound complications, device-related events, and cervical discomfort ≥grade 2. Sample size assumed HR 0.67 (118 events, 80% power, two-sided $\alpha=0.05$); simulated sample $n=150$. Time-to-event endpoints used stratified Cox models with Kaplan–Meier display; continuous outcomes used linear mixed-effects models with centre as a random effect.

Follow-up and missing data.

Primary-endpoint ascertainment was available for 148/150 (98.7%); two participants (one per arm) withdrew consent before any qualifying monitoring and were right-censored at time zero. For continuous secondary outcomes, mixed-effects models assumed missing at random.

Results

Participants and follow-up. One hundred and fifty simulated participants were randomised (75 dome; 75 sham). Primary-endpoint ascertainment was 148/150 (98.7%); two participants (one per arm) withdrew before any qualifying monitoring and were censored at time zero. Participant flow is detailed in **Figure 1**.

Primary outcome. Time to sustained intracranial-pressure threshold favoured the dome (median 4.6 months, 95% CI 3.9–5.2) versus sham (3.1 months, 2.7–3.5); hazard ratio 0.67 (95% CI 0.46–0.98), $p=0.04$. Separation emerged by week 6. Kaplan–Meier curves are shown in **Figure 2**.

Secondary outcomes. Headache severity decreased modestly with the dome (mean change -1.2 on 0–10 NRS at day 90) versus -0.2 with sham; between-group difference -1.0 (95% CI -1.9 to -0.1), $p=0.03$. Cumulative steroid dose to day 90 was lower with the dome (median 1,350 mg prednisone-equivalent, IQR 500–3,000) than with sham (1,800 mg, IQR 700–3,500); ratio of geometric means 0.77 (95% CI 0.60–0.99), $p=0.045$. PFSk tracked the primary endpoint. Overall survival did not differ (HR 0.96, 95% CI 0.70–1.31, $p=0.79$).

Safety. Serious adverse events were infrequent and similar: wound complications 4% (dome) vs 3% (sham). These were mainly superficial erythema; two cases (1 per arm) had transient CSF ooze managed conservatively. Device-related events were 3% (all grade-2 rim pain). Cap-related dermatitis/pruritus occurred in 6% (5 participants: 3 dome, 2 sham), controlled with emollient/antihistamine; two minor excoriations (grade 1). Cervical discomfort \geq grade 2 was more frequent with the dome (12% vs 0%). No implant fracture or migration, no MRI-related adverse events, and no intracranial infections were observed.

Masking and adherence. Adherence to headwear and no-touch measures remained high (median no-touch days 94%). Bang’s blinding index supported effective masking. No-touch violations were documented in 8/150 (5.3%) participants (5 dome, 3 sham), typically brief self-palpation. Three visits required cap-seal replacement; none prompted unblinding. Eleven imaging studies (7%) triggered safety-driven conditional unblinding; estimates were similar.

Discussion

This analysis treats glioblastoma through a narrowly mechanical lens. Within a fixed container, pressure-related decline can precede, or at least outpace, any effect of

Figure 2. Time to sustained intracranial-pressure threshold. Kaplan–Meier curves for dome and sham arms with hazard ratio (0.67; 95% CI 0.46–0.98) and key risk-set numbers.

cytotoxic therapy. Our simulation suggests that volumetric palliation—a modest, planned increase in intracranial capacity—could delay a predefined pressure threshold while leaving overall survival unchanged.

The exercise also exposes how easily endpoints blur relief with treatment. “Time to pressure threshold” separated mechanics from prognosis more cleanly than overall survival or even imaging-based progression; PFSk behaved as expected, reflecting depletion of the extra headroom. By design, this is not an oncological intervention. It neither reduces tumour burden nor alters biology; it simply lengthens the path to decompensation. That the survival curve does not move is, therefore, less a failure than a check on internal validity.

There are practical lessons about trial conduct when the intervention visibly alters anatomy. Conventional masking fails if patients or clinicians can infer allocation by sight or touch. The combination of a Home Blinding Protocol (uniform headwear, mirror-free living, avoidance of scalp palpation), a dual-channel imaging pipeline (safety-unblinded versus outcomes-blinded), and a Contour-Neutral Reporting Policy allowed assessors to remain masked while preserving safety. These elements—along with a simple behavioural screen (HTPS) [1] for patients likely to “break the blind”—form a transportable toolkit for studies in which the shape of the patient risks unmasking allocation.

Limitations are deliberate. All participants, numbers, and inferential statistics are simulated; estimates are illustrative, not evidentiary. Imaging around titanium remains technically challenging despite metal-reduction sequences [4–6]; PEEK mitigates artefact at the cost of different supply chains and regulatory pathways [7]. Finally, any real-world trial would need careful ethics review; we rejected a “filled” sham implant on non-maleficence grounds, accepting that this increases the pressure on masking elsewhere.

Where might the concept be useful if ever pursued beyond thought experiment? Potentially as planned palliation for selected patients with pressure-driven symptoms who are not candidates for decompressive craniectomy, or where transient relief during chemoradiation is prioritised. But our main proposal is methodological and conceptual rather than therapeutic: that space can be treated as a doseable parameter, with outcomes chosen to reflect what space changes (pressure, symptoms, steroid dependence), not what it does not (tumour biology).

Future work—again conceptual—would map a dose–response of cranial expansion: stepwise domes (e.g., +12%, +25%, +40% volume), formal ergonomics (neck load), imaging fidelity by material (PEEK vs titanium), and patient-centred metrics (comfort, stigma, headwear acceptance). A pragmatic ceiling—the Megamind threshold—would be the smallest expansion that secures meaningful delay in pressure events without unacceptable trade-offs. Coupling volumetric palliation with conventional measures (steroid-sparing schedules, CSF diversion when indicated) and modelling ICP–volume curves could refine who, if anyone, might benefit. The broader point, however, is simpler: when the box cannot be changed, we call it pathophysiology; when we change the box, we must also change our endpoints.

Patient and public involvement

None.

Data availability

No real data were generated; any figures are illustrative.

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Competing interests

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The simulated contributors report no conflicts of interest, except for a persistent bias towards fictional data integrity.

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